

Sci!lake

Scientific Lake

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Abstract

SciLake introduces an open Scientific Lake concept, featuring customizable components deployed across a federation of machines to create, interlink, and maintain domain-specific, community-managed Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs). This infrastructure provides a unified method for accessing and querying contained assets, enabling the development of value-added services to enhance knowledge discovery, research reproducibility, and other research-related routines. Domain experts can select and tailor components to their specific needs, making the architecture highly customizable.

Apart from the Scientific Lake concept, SciLake is also developing two indicative, discipline-tailored, value-added services that are showcasing the value of this concept in practice. The first service is designed to enhance the exploration of a specific scientific domain's knowledge space by leveraging the content of relevant SKGs. The second service focuses on enhancing research reproducibility within specific domains by utilising the contents of SKGs to provide insights on the reproducibility of associated research products.

This deliverable report outlines the final version of the integrated SciLake system, its distinctive subsystems consisting of individual components, API interfaces and portals, integrated and deployed at the end of March 2026.

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Abbreviation List

ABBREVIATIONS	
FoS	Field of Science
GDD	Graph Differential Dependency
GGD	Graph Generating Dependency
HIN	Heterogeneous Information Network
IIS	Information Inference Service
ProGGD	Graph Data Profiling with GGDs
R2PG-DM	Relational to Property Graph Direct Mapping
RAA	Research Artefact Analysis
RI	Research Infrastructure
SKG	Scientific/Scholarly Knowledge Graph
SKG-IF	Scientific/Scholarly Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework
TDM	Text and Data Mining
UI	User Interface

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the final integrated version of the SciLake system which implements the Scientific Lake concept as a tiered, federated ecosystem of software components. It supports the creation, enrichment, interlinking and exploitation of Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs). The system realises a highly customisable infrastructure in which domain experts can assemble and deploy tailored configurations of components on SciLake nodes to support community-managed SKGs and value-added services across diverse scientific domains.

The integrated architecture is organised into two main tiers. The Scientific Lake tier provides the core capabilities for importing, transforming, hosting and querying both domain-agnostic and domain-specific SKGs, including the OpenAIRE Graph and domain-specific graphs; this is demonstrated through four use cases within the project: Cancer Research, Neuroscience, Energy and Transport (including CCAM and Maritime sub-pilots).

On top of this foundation, the Applications tier delivers two families of value-added services: Impact-driven Discovery and Reproducibility Assistance. The core components of the impact-driven discovery bundle are BIP! Services and BIP! Spaces, which along with utility components combine citation-based indicators with SKG-driven annotations and topic-level analytics (via SciTo and SciNoBo Field-of-Science classification) to support domain-tailored knowledge exploration portals. The reproducibility assistance bundle leverages SciNoBo Research Artefact Analysis, domain-specific research entity extraction and linking, citation-level reproducibility assessment, multilingual article segmentation and link-recommendation components (sHINER, SciNeM) to characterise research artefacts, their usage, and the nature of their reuse within and across domains.

The integrated system has been co-designed and validated with the aforementioned pilot communities following an agile, feedback-driven process involving early prototypes, dedicated workshops and iterative refinement of data models, pipelines and user interfaces. Pilot deployments confirm that SciLake can support end-to-end workflows: from acquisition and transformation of heterogeneous research resources into SKGs, through enrichment and interlinking, to impact-aware discovery and reproducibility-focused analytics exposed via web interfaces and APIs.

Finally, the deliverable reports on the steps taken toward alignment with the evolving EOSC Node-based ecosystem and the SKG Interoperability Framework. SciLake components and datasets have been made discoverable through EOSC-connected repositories and integrated into the OpenAIRE Research Graph, while the Lake API and data models are being harmonised

with SKG-IF to facilitate broader reuse of the SciLake toolkits by external research infrastructures and services.

2. Introduction

The primary goal of scientific research is to deepen our understanding of the world and leverage this knowledge to enhance our lives in various aspects. Scientific insights play a crucial role in shaping modern society, propelling technological innovations, and stimulating economic growth. Moreover, scientific knowledge serves as a foundation for future scientific discoveries, enabling scientists to build upon the work of their predecessors.

However, scientific knowledge is fragmented and not always organised in a manner that facilitates discovery and the extraction of insights that are valuable for informed decision-making. Domain knowledge can be encoded in a variety of formats: while some can be structured and easily searchable, such as information encoded in databases, others are completely unstructured, such as the textual information found in scientific publications. Compounding these challenges, scientific results are frequently published in different languages, which can further impede the process of uncovering valuable information.

Modern data and knowledge management approaches offer potential solutions to these challenges. For instance, Knowledge Graph technologies can help scientists organise domain knowledge into formats that are easily accessible and queryable. This facilitates the development of value-added applications that can enhance various aspects of daily routines for researchers and other relevant stakeholders. However, transforming domain knowledge into a Scientific Knowledge Graph (SKG) presents significant challenges. Domain experts often lack the specialised technical expertise needed to perform this work independently. In addition, this work cannot be done by knowledge management experts alone since domain knowledge is critical to organise the respective information in a proper way.

To address such challenges, SciLake introduced an open *Scientific Lake concept*, comprising an array of customizable components that can be deployed and executed on a federation of machines (called SciLake nodes) to facilitate the creation, interlinking, and maintenance of domain-specific, community-managed SKGs, and to offer a unified method for accessing and querying the contained assets, enabling the creation of value-added services to enhance knowledge discovery and other routines important to the research community at large. Domain experts can select to leverage only those components that are valuable for their particular use cases and configure or tailor them accordingly. Moreover, each SciLake node can host different SciLake components according to the needs of the particular use case.

Hence, the whole architecture can be considered as a federated and highly-customizable computational infrastructure.

To demonstrate the practical application of this concept, SciLake developed two indicative value-added services, which can be tailored for different disciplines. The first service, delivered by WP3¹, is designed to enhance the exploration of a specific scientific domain's knowledge space by leveraging the content of relevant SKGs. These SKGs provide metadata for entities that are essential for describing the domain, as well as valuable information on the relationships between these entities. Additionally, indicators of the impact of related research products, such as publications and datasets, that can also be derived from the contents of the SKGs, were exploited by the service to provide valuable insights into the significance of various domain-specific entities. The second service, the outcome of WP4², focuses on enhancing research reproducibility within specific domains by utilising the contents of SKGs to calculate reproducibility indicators for associated research products. To generate these indicators, the service leveraged detailed information from scientific research outputs (enriched in the SKGs), such as the semantics of citations pointing to them. Additionally, the service is tailored to the unique characteristics of each domain and is equipped to handle text in multiple languages by utilising SciLake's automatic translation component.

In the following sections, all relevant technical details are elaborated. Section 3 elaborates on the design approach followed. In Section 4, technical details of the main systems and components of the respective infrastructure are presented. Section 5 outlines the final version of the integrated system while section 6 describes the current state of the integration with the EOSC ecosystem. Finally, in Section 7, we summarise the report.

¹ See also SciLake deliverable D3.2 "Final version of the smart impact-driven discovery service" (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18328002>).

² See also SciLake deliverable D4.2 "Final version of the smart reproducibility assistance service" (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18339328>).

3. Design

In this section, we elaborate on the process followed during the design of the integrated system of SciLake. It is also worth noting that this section is a slightly updated version of the respective section of Deliverable D1.2³ ("Initial integrated system").

A key objective of the SciLake project was to involve researchers closely in the design and development process from the earliest stages. Within the project, use-case representatives served as domain experts actively engaged in these activities. We placed significant emphasis on presenting early prototypes to these pilot representatives and gathering feedback specific to their use cases. The input from SciLake pilot representatives was also crucial, as the project aimed at providing services tailored to different scientific domains. These representatives brought real-life use cases from four diverse scientific fields: Neuroscience, Cancer Research, Transport Research, and Energy Research. This diversity ensured that the developed services were designed in a way so that they could be configured and customised to meet the needs of multiple large scientific communities, including those engaged in cross-disciplinary research and collaboration.

Based on the previous, we decided to follow a co-design, agile approach that would rely on early and rapid prototyping and receiving feedback from the pilots of the project on many occasions through flexible experimentation and collaborative activities. Design sketches, static mock-ups, and (when possible) working prototypes were used to test new concepts and provide realistic impressions of the respective functionalities. This process was driving software development efforts offering iterative refinements and establishing a common vision for the project and maintaining a coherent focus at all stages.

Moreover, we have designed a series of parallel activities to reinforce the aforementioned approach:

- We have collected early feedback from the pilot representatives to better understand the use cases they bring to the project and their special needs for the components and services to be developed by the project. This activity has been fully documented in Deliverable D1.1 ("Initial service requirements")⁴.
- In November 2023, we organised a hands-on workshop in Barcelona for the pilots of the project to better refine their use cases, receiving also feedback by the technical partners of the project about what can be supported by the various components of the architecture.

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/14501193>

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/8403180>

- We have drafted an internal document outlining a roadmap of the expected SciLake piloting activities in an attempt to improve the communication between technical partners and pilot representatives and make them all aware of the expected joint activities and their rough timeline. This is a living document, providing general concrete guidance on these activities while continuously refining focused subjects as needed.
- We have formalised a way of collecting information about the respective domain knowledge spaces and SKG data models using living documents (the approach is also elaborated in the roadmap document mentioned in the previous bullet).
- In November 2024, we organised four technical workshop sessions to refine the design of the pilot SKGs data models, map the SKG querying needs according to pilot use cases, provide feedback to the SKG enrichment approaches, and finalise the design of the Lake API.
- From April 2025 onwards, a biweekly virtual meeting to provide feedback for the refinement, customisation, and testing of the SciLake components was introduced.

The aforementioned approach was the one followed during the previous period helping SciLake members to determine and refine the architecture of the respective integrated system and the design of the various services, subsystems, and components.

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4. System overview

In this section, we present the high-level, conceptual architecture of the SciLake tiered ecosystem (Section 4.1) and outline its main tiers (Sections 4.2-4.3).

4.1. High-level, conceptual architecture

To demonstrate and validate the Scientific Lake concept (see also Section 2), the SciLake partners have designed and implemented a tiered ecosystem of software components. Some of these components implement core functionalities needed by the basic concept of the Scientific Lake, making up the “*Scientific Lake*” tier, while others, making up the “*Applications*” tier, can be combined to offer value-added services to researchers leveraging the core Scientific Lake components. Figure 1 illustrates the high-level, conceptual architecture of the aforementioned ecosystem.

Figure 1: High-level, conceptual architecture

Each tier of the architecture consists of several customisable software components that can be installed on selected machines within a computational cluster to form a deployment of the SciLake ecosystem. These components can be grouped into bundles based on their functionality.

The Scientific Lake tier includes two main bundles of components:

- “*Import and Transformation Components*” bundle: It contains components that facilitate importing structured or unstructured knowledge from external sources into the Scientific Lake and its organisation into Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) to facilitate accessing and querying. The bundle comprises a variety of components including

knowledge graph creation tools, text mining tools, data transformation tools, and scientific content acquisition tools.

- *“Data Access and Querying Components”* bundle: It contains components that assist users in maintaining, updating, accessing, and querying domain-specific and domain-agnostic scientific knowledge. The bundle includes, among others: graph mining tools and graph querying & analytics tools.

In general, the components of the Scientific Lake tier are responsible of hosting both all domain-specific SKGs (e.g., those created for each SciLake pilot) and domain-agnostic ones (mainly the OpenAIRE Graph⁵).

Moving to the Applications tier, the project has created two bundles of components:

- The *“Impact-driven Discovery service”* bundle: The components in this bundle aim to leverage scientific impact indicator technologies to facilitate researchers in navigating the vast knowledge space of the respective scientific domains. The bundle comprises a variety of components including: keyword-based search tools for research products (publications, datasets, etc.), multi-perspective impact-based ranking tools for research products, Fields-of-Science (FoS) classification tools for research products, topic evolution and trend identification tools, and impact propagation technologies. All the components in this bundle make use of the components in the Scientific Lake tier to access the required scientific knowledge space.
- The *“Reproducibility Assistance service”* bundle: The components in this bundle aim to leverage text and graph mining technologies to assist researchers in making their research more reproducible. To achieve this, the bundle leverages tools offering a variety of functionalities including, among others: automatic identification of missing links between research products (e.g., publications, datasets, software), classification of links between research products based on their semantics, calculation of the reproducibility level of research works (e.g., offering reproducibility badges or indicators) and so on. All components in this bundle make use of the components in the Scientific Lake tier to access the required scientific knowledge space.

Section 5 outlines the components that have been integrated into each of the aforementioned bundles. It is worth mentioning that the original classification of software components into bundles followed the division of the relevant tasks across work packages in the project plan, a distinction intended to facilitate the development phase of the SciLake project. As a result, some components currently within the bundles of the Applications tier could also fit (potentially more appropriately) within one of the bundles of the Scientific Lake tier. For instance, the research entity mentions extraction component in the Reproducibility Assistant

⁵ OpenAIRE Graph: <https://graph.openaire.eu>

bundle of the Application tier could also be placed in the “Import and Transformation Components” bundle of the Scientific Lake tier. However, in this report, we selected to keep the original component classifications.

4.2. Scientific Lake Tier

The Scientific Lake tier consists mainly of a deployment of the Scientific Lake service. As mentioned, a such deployment on a computational cluster essentially involves (a) installing the Knowledge Graph engine in various nodes of the cluster, each hosting (and making accessible) a different SKG, and (b) deploying and executing a selection of the various Scientific Lake components on various nodes of the cluster. The selection of the components is based on the needs of the use case of interest and the particularities of the respective knowledge domain.

The Scientific Lake tier is organised in a way that facilitates the discovery and consumption of the contents of the Lake. The former is facilitated by the SciLake catalogue component, which offers search and navigation capabilities for the respective ecosystem. The latter is possible due to the interoperability guidelines that are followed for the creation and extension of the SKGs hosted by the Lake and the [Open Lake API](#) that was designed and implemented following the respective specifications. In the following paragraphs we elaborate more on these subjects.

The starting point for any end-user interested in the Scientific Lake contents is the SciLake Catalogue. This component, positioned at the centre of the federated system (hosted by the D4science infrastructure), allows listing and searching for the Knowledge Graphs hosted on the nodes of the system, as well as for SciLake tools deployed on them. The catalogue makes available useful information for the previous resources, such as basic descriptions, specifications used, documentation, etc. The metadata collected for tools and services are influenced by metadata specifications for research services that have been used in the past by EOSC or similar initiatives, in an attempt to make their integration into the EOSC ecosystem easier.

Regarding offering a convenient environment to create, update, and maintain SKGs, deployments of the various components described in Section 5 are configured and ready to be executed on demand on a selection of cluster nodes. These tools either (a) transform knowledge from sources having different formats to create SKGs that can later be hosted on an instance of the Knowledge Graph engine (see also the conceptual diagram in Figure 1) or (b) are capable of further enriching existing SKGs with additional contents. The tools are

naturally heterogeneous, however containerisation is used to simplify their deployment process.

Regarding accessing and querying the Lake contents in a unified and powerful manner, [AvantGraph](#) implements the Knowledge Graph engine, which is at the heart of each SciLake node. Each SciLake ecosystem deployment includes multiple deployments of AvantGraph, each offering accessing and querying capabilities on top of a different Scientific Knowledge Graph (SKG). The following AvantGraph instances have been established:

- one for the domain-agnostic OpenAIRE Research Graph.
- five for domain-specific pilot SKGs: Cancer Research, Neuroscience, Energy, Transport-CCAM, and Transport-Maritime.

Both Neo4j and AvantGraph instances are maintained for each pilot graph to serve complementary roles: Neo4j provides a mature platform with extensive ecosystem tooling suited for application development and integration, while AvantGraph delivers superior performance for graph analytics workloads and provides fully integrated GraphAlgo algorithm support, essential for the impact analysis and discovery services built in WP3.

In order to ensure a common way of accessing graph data on every SciLake Node, a common **Lake API** was developed to be deployed on each node. The respective API specification is built upon Research Data Alliance's SKG Interoperability Framework⁶ (SKG-IF). This framework offers a metadata model for the most common entities covered by domain-agnostic research-related entities (such as publications, datasets, researchers, organisations). SciLake's API endpoints, parameters, and fields followed a consistent nomenclature and structure whenever possible. Simultaneously, given SciLake's focus on addressing the specific needs of various domains, the project provided extensions to this model to meet those needs based on the feedback from domain experts.

Based on the previous, SciLake's Lake API exposes a set of entity-focused, SKG-IF-compatible GraphQL queries through a unified endpoint. The API provides strongly-typed operations over the core scholarly entities (such as research products, agents, venues, and topics) and domain-specific enrichments, with rich filtering, pagination, and sorting capabilities. The Lake API translates GraphQL queries into optimised Cypher statements tailored to each pilot graph, ensuring query performance while still offering a high degree of expressiveness for building value-added services. The API operates over the multiple Scientific Knowledge Graphs of the project (Cancer Research, Neuroscience Research, Transport Maritime, Transport CCAM, and Energy Planning), and exposes a unified schema that is shared across these graphs and extended with domain-specific types. As anticipated, the Lake API is consumed by

⁶ SKG-IF: <https://skg-if.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

Application-Tier services, which use these GraphQL endpoints to access and integrate the Scientific Lake contents required by higher-level applications and user interfaces.

4.3. Applications Tier

Apart from the core components of the Scientific Lake Service described above, each SciLake Node is designed to be supplemented with deployments of components aiming to support the provision of value-added services for the research community. More specifically, the project was focused on two main categories of such services: [impact-driven discovery](#) services (elaborated in [D3.2](#)) and [reproducibility assistant services](#) (elaborated in [D4.2](#)).

These value-added services rely on combining different components that can produce valuable SKG enrichments or offer related end-user functionalities. These components are leveraging the Scientific Lake service via the APIs to access and/or analyse the SKG contents.

Regarding impact-driven discovery, a key outcome of the project has been the development of BIP! Spaces, a service designed to support the creation of customised knowledge discovery portals (referred to as “spaces”) tailored to the needs of specific user communities. Each space is designed to integrate and exploit the content of the OpenAIRE Graph alongside selected domain-specific graph enrichments, enabling targeted exploration within a particular thematic area. The project’s objective has been to develop one dedicated space for each pilot use case, incorporating the corresponding domain-specific SKG into each environment. After D1.2 submission, BIP! Services, and in particular BIP! Spaces, evolved into a fully operational and domain-adaptable discovery portal within the SciLake ecosystem. It served as a backbone for the project demonstrations, showcasing how citation-based analytics combined with knowledge graph technologies can deliver high-value, tailored services to domain experts.

Currently, the BIP! Spaces integrate with domain-specific Scholarly Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), enabling the enrichment of search results with annotations and domain-specific concepts. As a result, domain experts can explore the scientific literature not only through citation-based impact indicators but also through the terminology, entities, and relationships specific to their domain. It supports keyword-based search for research products (publications, datasets, software, and other products) combined with annotations coming directly from the determined SKG. Multiple annotation types are supported, while each of them corresponds to a particular graph query that can be served by the KG engine in which the SKG is loaded. As it is evident, the BIP! Space should be configured so that it is aware of a KG engine deployment to which it should be connected.

The BIP! Spaces also support topic evolution features. More specifically, SciTo, a topic evolution tool, was further developed and integrated into the BIP! Spaces platform, extending

the platform's analytical capabilities and supporting the exploration of topic-level insights derived from the scientific literature. Through this integration, users can interactively explore key topics within search results, analyse their publication and citation trends over time through statistical summaries, and visualise their evolution using ribbon charts and temporal plots, gaining deeper insights into the impact and emerging directions of research.

The FoS taxonomy was systematically aligned with the Scopus and EuroSciVoc taxonomies in order to assess coverage, granularity, and structural consistency. This process resulted in the release of SciNoBo Taxonomy V2, which addressed structural redundancies (e.g., single-child hierarchies and duplicated nodes), resolved cross-domain inconsistencies, and extended branches that previously terminated at coarse levels.

The FoS classifier was deployed and its results were integrated into the OpenAIRE Graph. Through this integration, the pilots were able to select the scientific publications that constituted parts of their Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs).

Regarding the reproducibility assistance service, the implementation of the end-user features was carried out in the form of badges of reproducibility and replicability integrated into the BIP! Spaces UI. The enrichments required to support these functionalities (e.g., the links between research products) were produced from the respective components and integrated into the OpenAIRE Graph or/and the domain-specific SKGs. Through the respective APIs they are being available to the respective value-added services.

The SciNoBo Reproducibility component was significantly extended and refined during the project. Key improvements included the formalisation and expansion of the underlying ontology, the creation of a multidisciplinary manually annotated dataset, the evaluation of multiple modelling paradigms, and enhancements to robustness and domain coverage across several fields (including in particular Energy, Neuroscience, Cancer, and Transport). In addition, a scalable architecture suitable for large-scale deployment was selected. In its final version within the SciLake project, the tool employs a SciBERT-based multitask model, balancing predictive performance with operational scalability. The outputs currently integrated into the Scientific Knowledge Graphs are generated using this model.

5. Main components overview

In this section we provide an overview of the main components included in the SciLake ecosystem. Each subsection outlines the components contained within the component bundles.

5.1. Import and transformation components (part of the Scientific Lake Tier)

In the following paragraphs we outline the main components that belong to the “Import and transformation components” bundle of the Scientific Lake tier.

5.1.1. SciLake Catalogue

To facilitate discovery within the SciLake ecosystem, a dedicated SciLake Catalogue⁷ serves as a central registry for information on all available Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) and tools. The SciLake Catalogue acts as a single point of access, fostering data discovery and governance. It achieves this by leveraging rich metadata descriptions for each resource, including details like location, provenance, and dependency information, regardless of where the resources are stored or running.

Figure 2: SciLake Catalogue home page

⁷https://services.d4science.org/web/scilake_lab/catalogue

The catalogue is hosted by the D4Science infrastructure, a long-standing and well-established e-infrastructure in the European and international Open Science landscape. D4Science provides a stable and sustainable environment for the management, publication, and discovery of research resources, thereby ensuring the persistence, availability, and long-term accessibility of the data exposed through the catalogue.

5.1.2. Information Inference Service

Information Inference Service (IIS)⁸ is a service, developed and maintained by ICM, encapsulating various mining modules including TDM modules based on the Madis framework⁹, an extensible relational database system, developed by Athena Research Center.

IIS is a flexible data processing system for handling big data based on Apache Hadoop¹⁰ technologies. It uses algorithms to extract new entities and relations from full texts to enrich SKGs. In practice, IIS defines data processing workflows that connect various modules, each one with well-defined inputs and outputs.

Throughout the SciLake project lifespan, IIS received several significant updates. One of the most relevant for the SciLake pilots was the integration with the Grobid¹¹ machine-learning library, which enables the refined extraction of text and metadata from PDF documents.

5.1.3. PDF Fetcher

This module, developed by OpenAIRE, is responsible for managing and optimising the process of obtaining PDF documents associated with publication graph entities. It delivers PDF documents as an input to the IIS where plaintexts are extracted, aggregated into the datasets and sent to the TDM modules for further processing. Additionally, the component feeds the full-texts to various other text mining components (e.g., those presented in Section 4.4.2). As of today (March 2026) it maintains over 60 millions of PDF and XML contents with almost 19 millions fulltexts relevant to SciLake pilots.

⁸ <https://github.com/openaire/iis>

⁹ <https://github.com/madgik/madis>

¹⁰ <https://hadoop.apache.org/>

¹¹ <https://github.com/grobidOrg/grobid>

5.1.4. Domain-Specific Machine Translation Models

The Machine Translation system ensures accurate and contextually appropriate translations by fine-tuning general-purpose machine translation models with domain-specific scientific data. This approach addresses the unique challenges of scientific discourse, such as specialized technical lexicons and complex syntactic structures, which often impair the performance of generic models. Three translation models were built within the project, to support the following language pairs: French to English, Spanish to English, and Portuguese to English. While the models provide robust performance for general scientific text, they have been specifically specialized for the four domains of the project pilots.

The models were generated by fine-tuning large pre-trained OPUS-MT transformer-based models. The curation process involved an end-to-end pipeline that processed approximately 9.3 million records from 62 academic repositories. This resulted in a substantial collection of 11.7 million parallel sentence pairs, primarily mined from the titles and abstracts of theses, dissertations, and scientific articles.

Evaluation results demonstrate that fine-tuning with domain-specific data, especially when supplemented with general scientific corpora, yields significant improvements in translation quality. On average, the fine-tuned systems outperformed baseline models by +2.4 BLEU and +1.6 COMET points.

The produced models are open-source and can be downloaded from the Hugging Face platform:

- **French-English:** huggingface.co/ilsp/opus-mt-big-fr-en_ct2_ft-SciLake
- **Portuguese-English:** huggingface.co/ilsp/opus-mt-pt-en_ct2_ft-SciLake
- **Spanish-English:** huggingface.co/ilsp/opus-mt-big-es-en_ct2_ft-SciLake

It is worth mentioning that these models are also being used by the Article segmentation for multilingual articles component that is being developed in the context of the Reproducibility Assistance service (Section 4.4).

Beyond the primary transformer-based MT models, the system optionally leverages Large Language Models (LLMs), specifically Gemma3-27b-it, for specialized translation tasks. This hybrid approach, as detailed in [D4.2](#), allows the integrated system to handle complex linguistic nuances that supplement the robust, domain-specific performance of the fine-tuned OPUS-MT engines.

5.1.5. Knowledge Graph creation assistant

The Knowledge Graph Creation Assistant Tool Bundle delivers a set of automated and semi-automated tools to facilitate the creation of SKGs following data acquisition. Use-case partners have different data sources, structured and unstructured, and utilise these tools to create their own pipeline for knowledge graph construction. Schema mapping tools transform (semi-)structured data to property graphs, while information extraction components handle unstructured data. To guarantee quality, the tool bundle is designed to be used by use-case partners as humans in the loop.

Figure 3: Knowledge Graph Creation Assistant Tool Bundle

R2PG-DM

R2PG-DM is a direct mapping that follows a natural, logical translation of relational databases to property graphs, preserving the schema and reasoning over basic properties of a direct mapping. Its semantics are defined declaratively using Datalog, enabling formal reasoning about correctness (information preservation, query preservation, and semantics preservation).

Since D1.2, R2PG-DM has been extended to support enterprise-scale deployments. Main improvements include:

- **Progressive execution and scalability:** through connection pooling, multi-threaded processing, and memory optimization, enabling processing of datasets up to 10GB scale factor (TPC-H) with over 90% runtime reduction.
- **Edge properties:** where join tables are identified and mapped to labeled edges with properties, enabling natural representation of many-to-many relationships.
- **PG-Schema output:** generating standardized schema descriptions compatible with the emerging GQL standard.

Source code is available at github.com/avantlab/R2PG-DM.

ProGGD

Graph Generating Dependencies (GGDs) are a class of integrity constraints for property graphs that capture both topological and property-value semantics. They are more expressive than prior formalisms (Graph Entity Dependencies, Graph Functional Dependencies), as they can enforce the existence of nodes, edges, or graph patterns - essential for property graphs where relationships are first-class citizens.

ProGGD is an interactive system for graph data profiling using GGDs. Its interface is organized into four panels: dataset metadata, attribute statistics, graph pattern exploration (via gCore queries), and GGD visualization with support, confidence, and coverage metrics. ProGGD is deployed as a multi-component system with SHINER as the backend for GGD validation and Apache Spark for scalable graph analytics. Source code and deployment instructions are available at github.com/avantlab/proggd.

Figure 4: ProGGD user panel

GDDMINER

GDDMiner addresses the automatic discovery of approximate GGDs: dependencies that hold in most of the data with a bounded degree of inconsistency. The framework operates in three steps: pre-processing (identifying important attributes and building similarity indexes), candidate generation (using a lattice structure with frequent subgraph mining), and GGD extraction (verifying candidates via a k-NN-based Candidate Index). Main innovation is the **Answer Graph**, a factorized representation of graph pattern matches that enables orders-of-magnitude improvements in execution time and memory efficiency. GDDMiner was validated on real-world datasets (Cordis, GDelt, DBLP) and synthetic benchmarks (LDBC), achieving 70–97% coverage and comparing favorably with AMIE+ rule mining while offering richer expressiveness.

Figure 5: GDDMiner workflow

5.1.6. Data interlinking component

The data interlinking component is mainly based on the functionalities provided by SciNeM and sHINER, two components that are also responsible for the link recommendation functionalities offered in the context of the Reproducibility Assistance service. Hence, the respective descriptions can be found in the respective subsection of Section 4.4.

5.1.7. Community Gateways

The Research Community Gateway is a service which fosters transparent evaluation of results and facilitates reproducibility of science for research communities by enabling a scientific communication ecosystem supporting exchange of research products (publications, research data, research software, methods) and links between them across communities and across

content providers. It is a Virtual Research Environment making it easy to share, link, disseminate and monitor publications, research data, research software, methods in one place. It simplifies the discovery of research products within a community, finding a repository to deposit research outcomes and linking research products with a community, funding stream or other research products.

The gateway also provides the capability to curate and expose content tailored to specific subcommunities within a broader research domain. As implemented for the CCAM and Maritime pilots, both were configured as subcommunities of the broader transport research community. This approach enabled the selection of content relevant to the specific needs of each pilot and allowed such content to be leveraged in the construction of the Scientific Knowledge Graph (SKG).

Figure 6: Transport Research Community Gateway

5.2. Data access and querying components (part of the Scientific Lake Tier)

In the following paragraphs we outline the main components that belong to the “Data access and querying components” bundle of the Scientific Lake tier.

5.2.1. Knowledge Graph engine

All Scientific Knowledge Graphs are instantiated by relying on AvantGraph, a specialized high-performance graph processing and analytics engine for scientific lake services. AvantGraph is deployed as a Docker image with full deployment instructions available at github.com/avantlab/avantgraph.

Figure 7: AvantGraph sub-components

AvantGraph supports a wide spectrum of data processing tasks, from subgraph pattern matching to general graph algorithms. It allows loading SKGs as Neo4j JSON/RDF and querying with Cypher/SPARQL, and can serve as a drop-in replacement for Neo4j through the BOLT protocol. Since D1.2, the engine has undergone significant development to meet pilot requirements:

- **Cypher enhancements:** string predicates for metadata filtering, aggregation functions for impact metrics, ORDER BY/SKIP/LIMIT for result pagination, and property indexes for fast lookup.
- **Performance improvements:** optimized factorization, zero-copy disk reads, and multi-threaded loading now enable processing of the full OpenAIRE Graph (hundreds of millions of edges).
- **GraphAlg integration:** GraphAlg, a domain-specific language for graph algorithms based on linear algebra, is now enabled by default. It allows embedding algorithms (e.g., PageRank, shortest paths, connected components) directly in Cypher queries via a WITH ALGORITHM clause, eliminating the need for costly data export/import workflows. GraphAlg programs compile to a unified intermediate representation shared with Cypher, enabling cross-optimization across query and algorithm boundaries. Benchmarks on the LDBC Graphalytics suite and the SciLake OpenAIRE energy planning dataset (47M edges) show competitive or superior performance compared to Neo4j and DuckDB, with 2–10× less code than SQL/Python alternatives.
- **Query optimization research:** The Magellan optimizer introduces seeding techniques for navigational graph queries (Regular Queries), achieving orders-of-magnitude speedups over state-of-the-art. A general cardinality estimation framework provides principled techniques for property graph query optimization.
- **GraphAlg Playground:** An interactive browser-based learning platform (compiled to WebAssembly) allows pilot domain scientists to learn and experiment with GraphAlg without installing database software (available at wildarch.dev/graphalg/playground).
- **Pilot deployments:** AvantGraph instances have been established for the domain-agnostic OpenAIRE Research Graph as well as for all five pilot-specific SKGs (Cancer, Neuroscience, Energy, Transport-CCAM, Transport-Maritime). A demonstration repository (github.com/avantlab/scilake-demo) provides documentation, examples, a Python API, and Jupyter Notebook integration for interactive analysis.

5.2.2. Lake API

The Lake API is a GraphQL web service that provides unified access to Scilake's Scientific Knowledge Graphs. It exposes research products and their domain-specific enrichments, allowing users to query research products, agents, venues, topics, funding and domain-specific entities through a single endpoint. The implementation is Open Source¹² and is provided under the GPL-v2 license.

HIGH-LEVEL ARCHITECTURE

The Lake API follows a layered architecture that separates presentation, query definition, data access, and graph storage. Conceptually (as shown in Figure 8), it consists of:

- *Data Storage Layer:* Multiple graph databases, each hosting a separate Scientific Knowledge Graph. All these pilot domain-specific graphs follow a shared SKG-IF-inspired core schema and add domain-specific enrichments relevant to their research areas (e.g., Diseases and Genes for Cancer Research, Techniques and Brain Parcellations for Neuroscience Research, Energy Storage Systems and Types for Energy Planning, and Vehicle and Vessel types for Transport CCAM and Maritime, respectively).
- *API Layer:* A GraphQL API that acts as the single entrypoint for clients. It exposes a unified schema that integrates both core entities (products, agents, venues, topics, grants, datasources, manifestations, PIDs) and pilot-specific entities. This layer is conceptually split into the Graph API and Resolver & Mapping subcomponents. The first one is responsible for schema definition, request handling, and validation of incoming GraphQL operations, while the latter translates GraphQL queries into Cypher queries, applying filtering, pagination, and sorting, and mapping database results back into the GraphQL response format.
- *Client Layer:* This layer includes any user-facing applications that communicate with the API over HTTP by sending GraphQL queries. These include browser-based tools (such

¹² Lake API source code: <https://github.com/athenarc/scilake-api>

as a GraphQL playground) as well as custom web applications and analytical services.

Figure 8: Lake API high-level architecture

Figure 8 illustrates this end-to-end flow when a GraphQL query is issued to the Lake API. First, the GraphQL API subcomponent validates it against the unified schema and reads a dedicated header to determine which Scientific Knowledge Graph to target. The resolver and mapping logic then constructs one or more Cypher queries tailored to the selected SKG, executes them against it, aggregates the results, and finally returns a structured JSON GraphQL response to the client.

TECHNOLOGY STACK AND SCHEMA DEFINITIONS

The Lake API is built in Python using a modern, lightweight stack for performance and maintainability, combining FastAPI for request handling, Strawberry GraphQL for type-safe schema definition, Neo4j or AvantGraph as graph database backends, and Uvicorn for asynchronous serving, all containerized using Docker containers. Its GraphQL schema reflects the conceptual model of the pilot SKGs, covering core scholarly entities, such as research products, agents, venues, topics, grants, datasources, and manifestations, while also allowing pilot-specific enrichments, including domain-specific concepts like genes and diseases for Cancer or techniques and brain regions for Neuroscience. This design enables clients to query both shared and domain-specific entities seamlessly, within the same requests.

QUERYING AND FILTERING CAPABILITIES

The Lake API leverages the flexibility of GraphQL alongside the expressive power of graph databases to support advanced exploration and analysis of the SKGs. Users can apply flexible filtering on many entity properties, including exact matches, partial string matches, list-based conditions, and nested logical combinations using AND/OR operators. Filters can also span multiple entity types, enabling queries such as retrieving all products authored by a specific agent that also reference a particular technology or domain-specific concept.

All queries provide pagination and configurable sorting, allowing efficient handling of large datasets and incremental browsing. GraphQL's selective field retrieval further enhances efficiency by enabling clients to request only the fields they need, reducing payload size.

The API supports multi-graph operation across multiple pilot knowledge graphs without separate endpoints. A simple graphdb header in each request selects the active graph while the server routes queries to the appropriate backend. This design promotes reuse of query logic across pilots and enables cross-domain comparisons at the application layer.

A key strength of the Lake API is its ability to expose and navigate the rich, interconnected graph structure. In a single query, clients can traverse between products, agents, venues, topics, and pilot-specific entities, supporting complex exploration and discovery workflows. To illustrate these capabilities, consider query in Figure 9, which retrieves research products associated with a specific technology while also keeping those that meet a certain citation count threshold.

Figure 9: Lake API GraphiQL interface

This query demonstrates several key features of the Lake API:

- *Nested logical filtering*: The AND clause combines multiple conditions across entities, here restricting results to products linked to the technology “smart traffic signals” and having more than two citations.
- *Cross-entity traversal*: By filtering on the technology entity, the query navigates from products to related technologies within the graph.
- *Pagination and field selection*: The query retrieves up to 100 results while selecting specific fields, including product metadata and related technology identifiers, avoiding unnecessary data transfer.
- *Exploration of rich relationships*: Users can access both core product properties (title, citation count, popularity) and related entities (technologies) in a single request, supporting comprehensive analytical and discovery tasks.

When executed in the GraphiQL interface, as illustrated above, this query shows how users can combine filtering, traversal, and selective retrieval to explore complex relationships in the Scientific Knowledge Graphs.

DOCUMENTATION AND ACCESS

The documentation page¹³ offers a comprehensive overview of the available knowledge graphs, their entities, and example queries to help users quickly understand the structure and capabilities of the API. It includes an interactive GraphQL environment¹⁴ where developers and researchers can explore the GraphQL schema through introspection, construct and execute queries, and experiment with different filters and query patterns. This interactive interface facilitates rapid prototyping and testing while also enabling users to better understand the relationships between entities, the underlying data model, and the full range of query options available.

5.3. Impact-driven Discovery service components (part of the Applications tier)

The following paragraphs describe the components of the Impact-driven Discovery service.

5.3.1. BIP! Services

BIP! Services is a suite of tools for scientific knowledge discovery, offering impact-aware ranking, filtering, and enrichment functionalities on top of large-scale scholarly knowledge graphs. The suite includes components that calculate and leverage advanced citation-based impact indicators to assist knowledge discovery, and can support tailored exploration scenarios for research communities.

At its core, BIP! aggregates citation data from the OpenAIRE Graph, constructing a large-scale citation network comprising more than 250 million research products, including publications, datasets, software, and other scholarly outputs. On top of this network, a set of distinctly different citation-based indicators is computed in a scalable manner (using Apache Spark). These indicators capture complementary dimensions of scientific impact, including popularity (current impact), influence (overall impact), and impulse (early momentum after publication). The computation of these indicators is performed by the BIP! Ranker component¹⁵, which lies at the core of the platform. The calculated metrics are provided as an open dataset on Zenodo¹⁶, as well as exposed through service APIs that support ranking and filtering functionalities in downstream applications.

¹³ Lake API documentation page: <https://scilake-api.athenarc.gr/>

¹⁴ Lake API GraphiQL UI: <https://scilake-api.athenarc.gr/graphql>

¹⁵ BIP!-Ranker, <https://github.com/athenarc/Bip-Ranker>

¹⁶ BIP! DB, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4386934>

Originally, the aforementioned capabilities were provided via BIP! Finder, a Web user interface designed to enable impact-aware academic search and facilitate scientific knowledge discovery. Within the context of the SciLake project, BIP! Finder¹⁷ was substantially adapted and extended into BIP! Spaces¹⁸, a domain-customisable service platform capable of supporting tailored exploration scenarios for specific scientific communities.

BIP! Spaces integrates with domain-specific Scholarly Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), enabling the enrichment of search results with annotations and domain-specific concepts. As a result, domain experts can explore the scientific literature not only through citation-based impact indicators, but also based on the specific terminology, entities, and relationships of their field.

BIP! Spaces has been validated through multiple domain pilots, including the Cancer Research Energy Planning, Neuroscience, and Transport (Maritime and CCAM) pilots. As illustrated in Figure 10, the platform supports advanced search and filtering functionalities combined with an impact-aware ranking scheme based on citation-based indicators (e.g., popularity, influence, and impulse). Search results are dynamically ordered according to the selected ranking selection, enabling users to explore the literature from different impact perspectives. In addition, each retrieved research product is enriched with domain-specific annotations derived from the corresponding Scholarly Knowledge Graph, providing relevant entities

¹⁷ BIP! Finder, <https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/search>

¹⁸ BIP! Spaces, <https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/spaces>

tailored to the needs of domain experts.

The screenshot displays the SciLake search interface. On the left, a sidebar contains filter categories: Popularity, Influence, Citation Count, Impulse, and Type. The search box contains the text 'sequencing'. The ranking scheme is set to 'Influence'. The search results show 88,012 results (4,401 pages). The first result is 'Ubiquitous somatic mutations in simple repeated sequences reveal a new mechanism for colonic carcinogenesis' by Yurij Ionov et al. (1993). The second result is 'Recurring Mutations Found by Sequencing an Acute Myeloid Leukemia Genome' by Ling Lin et al. (2009). The second result's 'Annotations' section is highlighted with a red box, showing tags for 'Diseases' (36), 'Drugs' (5), and 'Tissues' (22). The 'Tissues' tag is expanded to show a list of tissue types: astrocytoma cell line, hematopoietic stem cell, bone marrow, hematopoietic cell, blood plasma, hematopoietic system, blood platelet, animal, brain cell line, blood, marrow, whole body, acute myeloid leukemia cell, leukemia cell, brain cancer cell line, blast cell, connective tissue, blood cancer cell, adult stem cell, glioblastoma cell line, skeletal system, and myeloid leukemia cell.

Figure 10: BIP! Space for the SciLake cancer research pilot

Overall, BIP! Services, and BIP! Spaces in particular, have evolved into a fully operational, and domain-adaptable discovery portal within the SciLake ecosystem, acting as the backbone for the project demonstrations and showcasing how citation-based analytics combined with knowledge graph technologies can deliver high-value, tailored services to domain experts.

The source code of BIP! Finder and BIP! Spaces remains open source and publicly available at: <https://github.com/athenarc/bip-services>

5.3.2. SciTo

SciTo is a topic monitoring and analysis tool designed to support the exploration of scientific trends over time. It enables the identification, tracking, and visualisation of the evolution of research topics based on their associated research products and impact indicators. By analysing the mappings between research products and thematic concepts, SciTo provides insights into topic dynamics, growth patterns, and impact trajectories. These capabilities support researchers, policy makers, and funding organisations in understanding the development of scientific domains, identifying emerging research areas, and informing strategic decision-making processes.

Within the SciLake project, SciTo has been evolved and integrated into the BIP! Spaces platform (see also Section 4.3.1). As shown in Figure 11, users can interact with the top-5 key topics identified within a given search result set and explore detailed statistics for each of them, including the number of associated research products and their citation counts per year. This functionality enables experts to analyse the temporal dynamics and impact of specific topics directly within the discovery portal. Furthermore, by selecting the visualisation icon next to the top-5 topics, users can access the evolution of these topics over time (illustrated by Ribbon chart diagrams), presenting both publication volume and citation trends per year. Through this integration, leveraging the SciTo engine, BIP! Spaces extends beyond impact-aware search by offering interactive, topic-centric analytics that support deeper understanding of research trajectories and emerging trends.

Figure 11: Visualisation of topics evolution

5.3.3. SciNoBo FoS (Field of Science) Component

The SciNoBo Field of Science (FoS) component provides a unified framework for the classification and discovery of scientific publications. It consists of three elements: (a) the FoS Taxonomy, (b) the FoS Classifier, and (c) the FoS Taxonomy Mapper. Together, these enable pilots and external services to identify, organise and retrieve publications across multiple levels of disciplinary granularity.

FoS Taxonomy

The SciNoBo FoS Taxonomy is a hierarchical, multi-level classification scheme covering Levels 1–6. It builds upon the OECD/FORD (Frascati) classification for Levels 1–2 and integrates the SCIENCEMETRIX scheme at Level 3. Levels 4–6 are generated through AI-driven methods, including venue-based community detection, topic modelling and LLM-based labelling, enabling fine-grained and evolving research areas to be represented. More information is provided at D3.2.

During the SciLake project, the taxonomy was systematically aligned with Scopus and EuroSciVoc to assess coverage, granularity and structural consistency. This process led to the release of [SciNoBo Taxonomy V2](#), addressing structural redundancies (e.g. single-child hierarchies, duplicated nodes), resolving cross-domain inconsistencies and extending branches that previously stopped at coarse levels.

The FoS taxonomy is openly available:

Repository	https://github.com/iNoBo/scinobo-fos-taxonomy
FoS Taxonomy Viewer V1	Markmap URL
FoS Taxonomy Viewer V2	Markmap URL
Paper(s)	Nikolaos Gialitsis, Sotiris Kotitsas, Haris Papageorgiou. SciNoBo: A Hierarchical Multi-Label Classifier of Scientific Publications. WWW (Companion Volume) 2022: 800-809 Sotiris Kotitsas, Dimitris Pappas, Natalia Manola, Haris Papageorgiou. SCINOBO: a novel system classifying scholarly communication in a dynamically constructed hierarchical Field-of-Science taxonomy. Frontiers Res. Metrics Anal. 8 (2023)

Table 1: Links to the repository and publications related to the Field of Science Taxonomy.

FoS Classifier

The FoS Classifier assigns one or more FoS labels to publications using a multilayer graph-based approach. It operates under the premise that publications predominantly cite thematically related work. The classifier constructs a venue-publication-FoS graph and propagates field information from venues to publications using citation-based signals (references and citations). This allows classification up to Level 4 using minimal metadata (venue and citation information).

For deeper levels (L5-L6), topic modelling and LLM-generated scientific labels are employed. Words and n-grams derived from titles and abstracts are integrated into the inference graph, enabling fine-grained topic-level classification.

The classifier has been deployed and results are integrated to the OpenAIRE Graph, through which the pilots selected the scientific publications that constituted parts of their Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs). It is available as open-source software and as a containerised service:

Code repo	https://github.com/iNoBo/scinobo-fos-classification
Docker hub	https://hub.docker.com/r/intelligencenoborders/scinobo-fos-classification
Huggingface (HF) space	https://huggingface.co/spaces/iNoBo/scinobo-fos-classification
Paper(s)	Nikolaos Gialitsis, Sotiris Kotitsas, Haris Papageorgiou. SciNoBo: A Hierarchical Multi-Label Classifier of Scientific Publications. WWW (Companion Volume) 2022: 800-809 Sotiris Kotitsas, Dimitris Pappas, Natalia Manola, Haris Papageorgiou. SCINOBO: a novel system classifying scholarly communication in a dynamically constructed hierarchical Field-of-Science taxonomy. Frontiers Res. Metrics Anal. 8 (2023)

Table 2: Links to code, docker and demo repositories of the Field of Science Classifier.

FoS Taxonomy Mapper

The FoS Taxonomy Mapper enables semantic alignment between external field definitions (e.g. third-party taxonomies, user-provided keywords, pilot-specific vocabularies) and SciNoBo FoS labels.

In its final version, the mapper adopts a flattened representation of the taxonomy (Levels 1-5), treating each FoS label as an independent semantic unit. Each label is embedded using

the nomic-ai/nomic-embed-text-v1.5 model and indexed in Elasticsearch. The tool supports cosine-based dense retrieval, lexical (BM25) retrieval and hybrid retrieval with reranking (BAAI/bge-reranker-v2-m3). Empirical evaluation showed that pure dense retrieval with cosine similarity provides the most semantically coherent mappings.

The number of returned FoS labels (k) is configurable, enabling pilots to balance recall and precision depending on their needs.

The FoS Taxonomy Mapper is available at:

Code repo	https://github.com/iNoBo/scinobo-taxonomy-mapper
Docker hub	https://hub.docker.com/repository/docker/intelligencenoborders/scinobo-taxonomy-mapper/general
Huggingface (HF) space	https://huggingface.co/spaces/iNoBo/scinobo-taxonomy-mapper
Paper(s)	-

Table 3: Links to code, docker and demo repositories of the Field of Science Taxonomy Mapper.

5.3.4. Impact propagation

Impact propagation refers to the challenge of measuring the impact of research outputs other than publications—referred to as *research artefacts* and including e.g., datasets and software—using tailored indicators. Unlike publications, artefacts are acknowledged not only through formal citations but also through indirect references and informal mentions, and standard indicators often fail to capture the distinctive ways in which artefacts can generate influence. Furthermore, acknowledgement alone does not necessarily reflect influence in terms of artefact reuse. Recognising and differentiating these forms is essential for a more accurate assessment of artefact impact.

Leveraging the contents of the Lake and the tools developed within the Smart Reproducibility Assistance service—see D4.2¹⁹—a series of indicators is proposed to capture different dimensions of artefact impact, in addition to classical citation counts and usage statistics such as views and downloads. These include indirect citation counts—citations to the publication introducing a given artefact—and informal in-text mentions. These have been implemented in BIP! Ranker—see D3.2²⁰. Further semantic information can be fetched from the outputs of the WP4 components, allowing for an exploration of the degree of reuse of the artefacts beyond

¹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18339329>

²⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18328003>

views and downloads. On top of this, a composite indicator is proposed that takes into account all these forms of acknowledgement and their intent, prioritising and assigning more weight to reuse over contextual references.

We have also run correlation experiments to understand how different ways of counting citations affect the ranking of research outputs—see D5.2²¹ for details. The first experiment explored whether moving from direct to indirect citations produces meaningfully different rankings, finding that the two approaches identify almost entirely different sets of top-ranked entities. A further comparison with usage metrics (views and downloads) finds a positive yet small correlation between these and indirect citations.

The second experiment, leveraging the output of the citance analysis component, explored finer-grained design choices in citation counting, using four variants along two main dimensions: (i) whether citances are counted uniquely per node pair or all occurrences are considered, and (ii) whether all citances are included or only those classified as non-refuting. Using the data from the project pilots, variants along the first dimension produced modest effects, while the exclusion of refuting citations had almost none.

These results, in addition to follow-up experiments, will be reported in a publication within the coming months.

5.4. Reproducibility Assistance service components

In the following paragraphs we outline Reproducibility Assistance service subcomponents.

5.4.1. SciNoBo Objects Recommendation

The Research Artefact Extraction tool is powered by the SciNoBo Research Artefact Analysis (RAA) framework. It identifies mentions of research artefacts (e.g. datasets, software) in scientific texts, extracts structured metadata (e.g. name, version, licence, URL), classifies usage and ownership, and deduplicates mentions to produce a unique list of artefacts referenced, used, or introduced in a publication.

Methodological Evolution

As detailed in [D4.1](#), the initial version of the tool relied on a Question Answering (QA) formulation based on fine-tuned Large Language Models (LLMs), combined with an optional Coreference Resolution Longformer model (SciCo), as well as discipline-specific keyword lists, key phrases, and gazetteers to detect candidate artefact mentions. Although this approach demonstrated strong results and we also experimented with a Llama3.1 variant, the use of

²¹ <https://zenodo.org/uploads/19347350>

LLMs proved computationally expensive and time-consuming for the large-scale processing required by the project.

To address scalability and efficiency constraints, research artefact recognition was reformulated as a Named Entity Recognition (NER) and classification task, leveraging transformer-based models pretrained on scientific text. In particular, SciBERT was adopted as the primary backbone model, enabling token-level detection of dataset and software mentions, improving robustness across disciplines, and significantly reducing inference time.

The current pipeline therefore combines:

- Transformer-based NER for artefact mention detection,
- Metadata extraction and usage/ownership classification,
- Optional coreference resolution (SciCo),
- Gazetteers and discipline-specific linguistic resources,
- Optional Deduplication mechanisms to ensure unique artefact representation.

Refer to D4.2 for how the tool was domain adapted to the Scilake pilots through Data Augmentation and LLM-as-a-judge techniques.

Figure 12: An overview of how the SciNoBo RAA tool works (pt1)

Figure 13: An overview of how the SciNoBo RAA tool works (pt2)

The Research Artefact Analysis tool is available at:

Paper(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empowering Knowledge Discovery from Scientific Literature: A novel approach to Research artefact Analysis • Streamlining Knowledge Discovery in Scientific Literature: A Comprehensive End-to-End System for Research Artefact Analysis (submitted to EMNLP 2024)
Code repo(s)	github.com/iNoBo/scinobo-raa
Docker hub	hub.docker.com/repository/docker/intelligencenoborders/scinobo-raa/general
HF Space (Demo)	huggingface.co/spaces/iNoBo/scinobo-research-artefact-analysis

Table 4: Links to code repositories and documentation of the field extraction component.

5.4.2. Research entity mentions

This service aims to identify mentions of domain-specific entities of interest in publications and in the textual descriptions of other research outputs, and to normalise these mentions with persistent identifiers through the linking with established taxonomies or ad-hoc domain-specific vocabularies created within the project. The initial version of the service consisted in a NER module focused on a set of core biomedical entities, based on the AIONER annotation scheme. This collection of entities was used in the context of the cancer pilot.

For the rest of the use cases of the project, we set up a pipeline that leveraged LLM-based pseudo-annotation with a human-in-the-loop approach to generate a small sample of annotated documents validated by the domain experts for each of the pilots. These samples were used to train a RoBERTa model and to fine-tune a GLiNER mode. Based on performance metrics and qualitative exploration, each community chose the model that worked best for their needs to be used for data integration.

An entity linking module operates on the output of the NER module, processing the entities that have been identified and linking them to the taxonomies of choice. This module has two stages:

1. **Candidate retrieval:** For each entity mention, candidate concepts are retrieved from the target vocabulary using embedding-based semantic similarity.
2. **Validation and ranking:** Retrieved candidates are validated using a language model that considers both the entity mention and its surrounding context from the source document.

In addition to the above, a direct one-step linking is achieved by a gazetteer-based approach.

Figure 14: Example output showing entities identified by the NER module and linked to controlled vocabularies by the linking module, for the case of the Maritime pilot.

Code repo(s)	github.com/sirisacademic/scilake-enrichments
Model files	huggingface.co/collections/SIRIS-Lab/scilake

Table 5: Links to code repositories and model files pertaining to the domain-specific entity extraction and normalisation pipeline.

5.4.3. SciNoBo Reproducibility

The SciNoBo Citation-context Assisted (CA) Replication Assessment tool provides a fine-grained analysis of citation mentions (citances) in scientific publications. By analysing the textual context in which a citation appears, the tool characterises how prior work is referenced, reused, extended, supported, or challenged.

Rather than relying solely on citation counts, the CA tool enables a multidimensional assessment of scientific reuse, validation, and rebuttal, supporting reproducibility and replicability analysis across research domains.

Since the initial version presented in [D4.1](#), the component has been significantly extended and refined, including:

- A formalised and expanded ontology
- A multidisciplinary manually annotated dataset
- Evaluation of multiple modelling paradigms
- Improved robustness and domain coverage (Energy, Neuroscience, Cancer, Transport)
- Selection of a scalable architecture for large-scale deployment

Each citance is analysed along three orthogonal dimensions:

1. Citation Intent

Captures the author's purpose in citing prior work:

- Generic – Background or contextual reference
- Reuse – Direct reuse of methods, artefacts, or approaches
- Comparison – Explicit comparison with related work
- Extension – Building upon or extending prior work

2. Citation Polarity

Captures the stance toward the cited work:

- Supporting
- Neutral
- Refuting

3. Citation Semantics

Captures the referenced aspect of the cited work:

- Claim – Conceptual statements, hypotheses, theories

- Results – Empirical findings
- Methodology – Experimental or analytical procedures
- Artifact – Datasets, software, tools, models

Each citance receives exactly one label per dimension, allowing independent or joint analysis. This representation enables identification of citations that signal methodological reuse, artefact reuse, validation of claims, extension of prior approaches, or refutation. Examples from the above classification ontology are presented in the following Figure:

Figure 15: Example citances and their corresponding classifications across the Semantics, Intent, and Polarity categories, based on the ontology defined in this work. Each citance mark in the same sentence can have similar or different categories.

The final version of the tool, in the context of the Scilake project, utilizes a **SciBERT-based multitask model**, taking into account both predictive performance and operational scalability. The outputs currently integrated into the Scientific Knowledge Graphs are generated using this SciBERT multitask model.

The Citance Analysis tool is available at:

Code repo(s)	https://github.com/iNoBo/scinobo-citance-analysis
Docker hub	https://hub.docker.com/repository/docker/intelligencenoborders/scinobo-citance-analysis/general
HF Space (Demo)	https://huggingface.co/spaces/iNoBo/scinobo-citance-analysis

Table 6: Links to resources corresponding to the citance analysis component.

5.4.4. Article segmentation for multilingual articles component

This component is mainly based on the DoStRe software, but it also leverages the automatic translation models developed in the context of the Scientific Lake service (Section 4.2).

DoStRe (Document Structure Recognition) is a tool that recognizes the structure of scientific documents. The objective of this tool is the recognition of the structure of scientific documents, especially identifying its constituent parts (sections and titles), coupled with the classification of these parts into predefined section types—e.g., the conclusions in a scientific paper could be named in many ways, such as ‘Conclusions’, ‘Conclusions and Future Work’, ‘Discussion’, etc. This problem is even more interesting if we look at multilingual papers.

This functionality is depicted in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Article Segmentation for scientific articles.

SCIENTIFIC ARTICLE STRUCTURE DETECTION (SEGMENTATION)

As described in D4.1, the first step in the pipeline leverages GROBID²² to process PDF documents and identify their structural components, such as headings, texts, tables, etc., offering three output formats: XML format using TEI schema; JSON format using TEI schema; and RDF format mapped from TEI. In Table 7 an XML example output of Grobid is shown.

The tool is provided as a docker container so that it can be utilised completely independently, without any special configuration needed.

```
<teiHeader xml:lang="en">
  <fileDesc>
    <titleStmt><title level="a" type="main">Organization of Posterior Parietal-Frontal
Connections in the Rat</title></titleStmt>
    <publicationStmt>
      <availability status="unknown"><licence/></availability>
      <date type="published" when="2019-08-21">21 August 2019</date>
    </publicationStmt>
    <sourceDesc><biblStruct><author><persName><forename
type="first">Gilad</forename><surname>Silberberg</surname></persName></author>
</biblStruct></sourceDesc></fileDesc>
  <profileDesc>
    <abstract><div xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0"><p>Recent investigations of the rat
posterior parietal cortex (PPC) suggest that this region plays a central role in action control
together with the frontal cortical areas. [...] </p></div></abstract>
  </profileDesc>
</teiHeader>
<text xml:lang="en"> <body> [...]
```

Table 7: XML Example of the output of Grobid.

SCIENTIFIC ARTICLE SECTION CLASSIFICATION

During the second half of the project, we have redefined the architecture of this component (shown in Figure 17).

We have trained five domain specific hierarchical text classifiers to automatically assign each part of the text to a predefined section class, based on a self-defined and annotated dataset, namely SASC dataset. This dataset has been annotated using a self-defined 2-level taxonomy for a hierarchical section classification approach. The 2-level taxonomy is presented in Table 8.

²² github.com/kermitt2/grobid

Figure 17: Scientific Article Section Classification.

ID	L=1 Class Label	L=2 Class Label	Description
1	Introduction	background, problem statement, objectives, contributions, outline	Context, problem statement, research gap, and paper goals. Corresponds to I in IMRaD.
2	Related Work	literature review, theoretical framework, gaps identified	Review of prior literature and state-of-the-art methods.
3	Method	study design, participants, data collection, procedures, statistical analysis, ethical considerations, materials and instruments, data preprocessing, evaluation, case study	Description of the system, materials, models, or procedures used. Corresponds to M in IMRaD.
4	Experiment	descriptive statistics, main findings, secondary findings, tables figures, statistical tests, evaluation	Details on experimental setup, data, metrics, and results. Closely tied to R in IMRaD.
5	Discussion	interpretation, comparison literature, implications, limitations, strengths, future work	Interpretation, implications, limitations, and future work. Corresponds to D in IMRaD.
6	Conclusion	summary, key findings, contributions, final remarks, future directions recommendations	Final summary of findings and concluding remarks.
7	Other	-	Unclassified sections.
8	Appendix/Misc.	supplementary data, additional analyses, technical details, code and materials, ethics and consent, compliance statement	Supplementary or procedural material directly related to the study: extended analyses, code, data, technical documentation, and ethical or compliance statements to the research process.
9	Metadata	acknowledgments, authorship, funding, license, data code materials availability, publisher note	Sections providing administrative or provenance information about the publication itself: author roles, funding sources, legal licenses, and data-sharing declarations. Not part of the scientific argument but essential for transparency and reproducibility.

Table 8: 2-level taxonomy defined for the SASC dataset (shows labels from levels 1 and 2).

The multilinguality is supported by the usage of multilingual models as a base for the classification part of the tool.

USEFUL RESOURCES

The next table (Table 9) summarises the most important resources (publications, code repositories, etc) related to the DoStRe component.

Paper(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Scientific Article Section Classification (SASC) Dataset. Accepted at LREC 2026.• Normalizing section names and structure of scientific articles. Accepted at NSLP 2026.
Code repo(s)	https://gitlab.com/dfki-scilake/dsr
Docker URL	registry.gitlab.com/dfki-scilake/dsr:d41

Table 9: Links to code repositories and documentation of the DSR component.

5.4.5. Link recommendation component

SHINER FOR ENTITY RESOLUTION

The sHINER system implements GGD-based entity resolution for property graphs. GGDs combine topological constraints (graph patterns) with differential constraints (attribute similarity measures), providing an explainable approach that addresses limitations of both embedding-based methods (which lack interpretability) and traditional logic-rule methods (which ignore graph topology).

Figure 18: sHINER Components

sHINER comprises two main components: the G-Core language interpreter, built on Apache Spark for scalable distributed processing, and the GGDs component, which implements validation and graph generation algorithms. Given a set of GGDs and an input graph, sHINER identifies violations and repairs the graph by generating missing edges or nodes specified in the target pattern. Two validation algorithms are implemented using left anti-joins and left outer joins, with the anti-join variant showing better scalability on LDBC benchmarks.

In the Cancer pilot, a GGD encodes the matching rule: when a Publication from the Clinical Knowledge Graph and a Result (of type Publication) from the OpenAIRE Graph have DOIs within edit distance ≤ 1 , they represent the same real-world publication and should be linked via a sameAs edge. These linking edges are generated automatically during graph repair. More broadly, sHINER supports interlinking heterogeneous graphs such as the OpenAIRE Graph with domain-specific external resources (e.g., CKG, EBRAINS) by applying GGD-based entity resolution to identify and generate missing relationships, followed by validation of the integrated graph against structural constraints.

Since D1.2, sHINER has been enhanced with a REST API mode for integration with the ProGGD interface, enabling interactive exploration of entity resolution results. Source code is available at github.com/avantlab/gcore-spark-ggd.

SciNeM

SciNeM²³ is an open-source system designed to support the exploration and analysis of Knowledge Graphs. It leverages Apache Spark to enable scalable, and distributed computation, allowing it to efficiently process large-scale graphs. At its core, SciNeM incorporates a range of graph algorithms, all implemented with scalability in mind to support execution in computational clusters. Its modular design facilitates extensibility, enabling the integration of additional analytical methods and functionalities. Given a metapath query and specific constraints on the involved entity types, SciNeM supports multiple analytical operations, including ranking entities through random walk-based approaches, identifying the top-k most similar pairs of entities, retrieving entities that are most similar to a given query node, and detecting communities within the graph structure.

Figure 19: SciNeM's main components

Within the context of the SciLake project, particular emphasis has been given on exploiting SciNeM's capabilities to uncover latent relationships between nodes in the knowledge graph. Rather than relying solely on explicitly defined links, SciNeM has been systematically employed to identify indirect associations through metapath-based exploration, enabling the discovery of meaningful but previously unobserved connections between research products and domain-specific entities. Specifically, in the Cancer Research pilot, SciNeM was applied to investigate implicit relationships between entities in the graph. In this case, Genes are not directly connected to research products in the graph schema. To address this limitation, SciNeM was used to trace indirect connections by following metapaths that traverse intermediate entities, such as Proteins, thereby enabling the inference of associations between Genes and research outputs. The inferred links were subsequently presented to users through the BIP! Spaces interface as part of the available annotations.

²³ <https://github.com/athenarc/SciNeM-workflows> and <https://github.com/athenarc/SciNeM>

6. EOSC integration

Since the time of the project proposal preparation and the start of the project, the EOSC landscape has undergone a significant philosophical and architectural overhaul, rendering many solutions planned and developed prior to these changes misaligned with the new framework. This shift directly impacted the SciLake project, which launched over a year before the formal introduction of the EOSC Node concept²⁴, described in detail in the EOSC Federation Handbook²⁵

While the components developed within SciLake are candidates for adoption by the EOSC Node services, ensuring full compliance with the new requirements will necessitate additional technical alignment.

To facilitate the integration of outcomes from WP2, WP3, and WP4 into the EOSC ecosystem, both software components and datasets have been made discoverable through the EOSC discovery layer. Specifically, datasets were deposited in Zenodo²⁶, an EOSC-connected repository, to ensure maximum findability. Consequently, the metadata for these datasets and software assets has been integrated into the OpenAIRE Research Graph. As the primary knowledge base for European research outputs, this graph serves as the foundation for the EOSC search engine, ensuring SciLake's contributions remain visible and accessible within the EOSC infrastructure.

Beyond ensuring the discoverability of project outcomes, the SciLake team has actively contributed to the evolution of EOSC standards through direct participation in strategic Working Groups. A primary focus of this engagement is the Scientific/Scholarly Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF)²⁷.

As a specialized data model, SKG-IF is designed to harmonize interoperability between diverse knowledge graph systems and research platforms. By defining a shared language and standardizing operations, it facilitates the seamless exchange and reuse of data across disparate environments. Within the context of the project, this framework serves as a foundational pillar for data exchange, enabling various knowledge graphs to leverage the specialized toolkits developed as core SciLake outcomes.

²⁴ <https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation>

²⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/14999577>

²⁶ <https://zenodo.org/>

²⁷ <https://skg-if.github.io/>

7. Conclusions

The integrated SciLake system is realising the Scientific Lake concept as a federated, tiered ecosystem of components for creating, enriching, interlinking and exploiting Scientific Knowledge Graphs across multiple domains. It consolidates the work of several work packages into a coherent architecture, with the Scientific Lake tier providing core import, transformation and querying capabilities, and the Applications tier delivering impact-driven discovery and reproducibility assistance services on top of this foundation. The resulting infrastructure demonstrates that heterogeneous research resources can be systematically transformed into interoperable SKGs and exposed through unified interfaces to support advanced analytical services.

Throughout the project, the design and implementation of the integrated system were guided by close collaboration with four pilot communities: Cancer Research, Neuroscience, Energy and Transport (including CCAM and Maritime). Their real-world use cases shaped the data models, pipelines, tools and user interfaces, ensuring that the resulting services address concrete needs such as navigation of complex knowledge spaces, monitoring of research impact, and assessment of reproducibility signals. Pilot deployments have confirmed that SciLake can support end-to-end workflows, from data acquisition and graph construction up to domain-tailored discovery portals and reproducibility-oriented indicators.

Apart from delivering a functioning integrated system, SciLake has also laid important groundwork for sustainability and wider adoption. The alignment of data models and APIs with the Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework, the integration of results into the OpenAIRE Research Graph and EOSC-connected infrastructures, and the open availability of several components position SciLake for reuse and extension by other communities and research infrastructures. Future work can build on this foundation to further extend domain coverage and foster a broader ecosystem of third-party tools and applications leveraging the Scientific Lake concept.